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EVALUATION OF INSTANT EFFECT OF *SHANKHAPRAKSHALANA* – A PILOT STUDY ON HEALTHY VOLUNTEERS

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Abstract

Laghu shankhapraksha has identified as a short version of *Poorna Shankhaprakshalana* which promotes the normal functions of the intestines. The five most common *Asanas* has to performed each (exercises) eight times which are *Tadasana, Tiryaka Tadasana, Katichakrasana, Tiryaka Bhujangasana, and Udarakarshanasana*. This study was focused primarily on *Laghu Shankha Prakshalana* (LSP) as a *Yogic* intervention in Healthy volunteers. Aim of this study was to evaluate the instant outcome of practicing *Laghu Shankhaprakshalana* among the healthy volunteers. This case series is intended to the healthy volunteers who were willing to practice the *Shankaparakshalana* in the purpose of health enhancement. There were female volunteers' aged between 20yrs to 50years. All the participants were made to practice this with the same protocol. Procedure was practiced in the steps of *Purva Karma, Pradhana Karma* and *Pashchat Karma* following the *Yogic* diet and other instructions accordingly. During the procedure, vitals and frequencies of *Vega* were assessed as per their *Prakriti*. *Prakriti* assessment was done according to the CCRAS *Prakriti* Portal (Central Council of Research in *Ayurvedic* Sciences). *Mala Vega* of 80% of them were onset after drinking the 4th and 8th glasses of water and of all the participants ends up the *Mala Vega* with pale colour watery without particles. It was found that blood pressure and pulse rate were reduced significantly after practicing the procedure of *LSP*. It can be concluded that the practice of this has effect on the vitals-pulse and blood pressure. The participants experienced the cleansing of digestive tract giving them physical and mental relaxation. Based on *Prakriti*, it was noted that the onset of *Mala Vega* and the onset of frequency was earlier and moderately high among the participants with *Kapha Pitta* dominant

Key Words:

Healthy volunteers, *Prakriti, Shankaparakshalana, Vital Parameters*

INTRODUCTION:

Ayurveda not only addresses the treatment of diseases but also places a strong emphasis on prevention through the maintenance of individual health, based on one's *Prakriti*¹. Essential *Ayurvedic* guidelines such as *Dinacharya* (daily routine), *Ratricharya* (night routine), *Ritucharya* (seasonal regimen), *Sadvritta* (ethical conduct), and *Rasayana Karma* (rejuvenation therapy) are central to the concept of *Swasthasya Rakshanam*—the preservation of health. In addition to *Ayurvedic* routines, *Yogic* texts like the *Hatha Yoga Pradipika* and *Gheranda Samhita* outline six major *Shatkarma* (cleansing practices): *Dhauti*, *Basti*, *Neti*, *Trataka*, *Nauli*, and *Kapalabhati*^{2,3}. These practices aim to purify the internal systems and prevent diseases. According to the *Gheranda Samhita*, *Antar Dhauti* includes four types: *Vatasara*, *Varisara*, *Agnisara*, and *Bahishkrita*⁴. *Varisara Dhauti* is a type of *Antara Dhauti*. *Dhauti* refers to “Internal washing”, and *Vari* means “water”. Researchers have mentioned that the term “*Shankha prakshalana*” is applied to it nowadays. *Shankha* means “conch”, and *Prakshalana* means “to wash completely”. The word *Shankha* is used to represent the entire alimentary canal from mouth to anus. It is a technique by which all the toxic materials accumulated in the gastro-intestinal canal are washed out⁵. It has identified that there are two types of *Shankhaprakshalana* which is mentioned as *Laghu shankhaprakshalana* and *Poorna Shankhaprakshalana*⁶. *Laghu shankhapraksha* is identified as a short version of *Poorna Shankhaprakshalana* which promotes the normal functions of the intestines⁷. The five most common *Asanas* has to performed each (exercises) eight times which are *Tadasana*, *Tiryaka Tadasana*, *Katichakrasana*, *Tiryaka Bhujangasana*, and *Udarakarshanasana*. Hence, the review is focused primarily on *Shankhaprakshalana/Laghu Shankha Prakshalana* (LSP) as a *Yogic* intervention in this study⁸.

Some studies have shown that diet along with *Yoga* practice expedites the reduction of weight and practicing *Laghu Shankhaprakshalana* (LSP) once a week for four weeks there is a significant decrease in constipation score and improved bowel health⁹. By practicing LSP once every 10 days for 4 months can improve Irritable Bowel Syndrome, Anxiety Neuroses, and Thyrotoxicosis. Some studies have shown it can reduce blood glucose levels, lower BMI, increase glutathione and vitamin C levels, and contribute to overall health normalization¹⁰. Another study found that weekly practice of *Laghu Shankhaprakshalana* (a milder version) reduces hypertension, fatigue, and anxiety, while improving sleep quality⁷. A study demonstrated that consistent practice over four months can significantly improve symptoms of Irritable Bowel Syndrome⁹. Further studies shows that practice of *Laghu Shankhaprakshalana* along with pure vegetarian diet, it helps to tone the intestinal tract, eliminate excess toxins, and reduce obesity, cholesterol, and lipid levels¹¹.

Patient Information

This case series is intended to the healthy volunteers who were willing to practice the *Shankhaprakshalana* for the purpose of health enhancement. There were female volunteers' aged between 20yrs to 50years. All the participants were made to practice this with the same protocol. During the procedure Vitals and frequencies of *Vega* were assessed as per their *Prakriti*. *Prakriti* assessment was done according to the CCRAS *Prakriti* Portal (Central Council of Research in *Ayurvedic* Sciences)

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of the Participants

Volunteers	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6
Gender	Female	Female	Male	Female	Female	Female
Age	24yrs	21yrs	26yrs	42yrs	43yrs	48yrs
Educational	Postgraduate	Postgraduate	Postgraduate	Postgraduate	Postgraduate	Postgraduate

level						
Scio-economic status	Middle class					

Timeline

Under expert supervision, procedure was carried out together for all the participants. Procedure was started early in the morning with empty stomach after completing daily morning routine.

Procedure

Selected six volunteers were made to practice *Laghu Shankaprasshalana* procedure. Their vitals were measured before and after completion of the procedure. During the process, onset of frequency of urges was observed. Procedure was practiced in the steps of *Purva Karma*, *Pradhana Karma* and *Pashchat Karma* as follow.

1. *Purva Karma*¹²

Participants were advised to eat only *Khichdi* (thin rice gruel), avoid junk food and heavy fried food in the previous night. Study subjects were advised to eat dinner between 7 p.m. and 8 p.m. and sleep early. They were advised to pass the natural urges and take bath before starting the process and it was started at 6 a.m. Before starting the procedure they were made aware and taught about the *Asana* to be performed.

Requirements for *Shankaprasshalana*:

Clean and hot water

Saindhava lavana

Khichari (rice, moong daal, go ghrita)

Vessel for drinking water

Toilet

Preparation of saline water (add 5gm salt/lit of lukewarm water)

2. *Pradhana Karma*

The process started early in the morning at about 6 a.m. *Prakriti* type was evaluated for each of them and measured the vitals of them and recorded and done the *Prakriti* assessment as per the CCRAS *Prakriti* evaluation procedure. Study subjects were advised to drink two glasses of Lukewarm Salt water(500ml) and were instructed to perform Yoga asana which are *Tadasana*, *Thiryak Tadasana*, *Kati-Chakrasana*, *Thiryak- Bujangasana* and *Udarakarshanasana* respectively. Each *Asana* should be practiced 8 times continuously before starting the next round. After completion of the first round it was advised them to drink again two glasses of water and continue the 5 *Asana* practicing repeatedly. Also advised them not take rest between rounds and repeat this process until they feel the urge to defecate. Study subjects were advised to leave the particular *Asana* and go to the toilet when urged to pass the stool. After coming back again they were advised to drink water and start from *Tadasana*. It was advised to continue drinking luke warm water, performing *Asana* and going to the toilet. Study subjects were advised to spend as little time in the toilet as possible. The aim is to build up the internal cleansing pressure. Solid stool is evacuated, followed by a mixture of stools and water. While the practice progresses, more water, and less solid stool are excreted eventually. At the end, only water is excreted. It was cloudy yellow water and almost clear water evacuated. But this can be varied from person to person.

3. Pashchat Karma⁹

After that they were advised to follow the *Kunjla Kriya* after 5-10 minutes of complete internal wash. Following steps were performed for the *Kunjla Kriya* :-

1) After 5-10 min of complete internal wash, 500 ml (2 glasses) of lukewarm saline water was given.

2) Stand and bend forward to vomit. Here use two fingers to rub the tongue as deep as possible which stimulates the vomiting. Then all the excess water in the stomach comes out through the mouth. At the end of the procedure, practice the *Shavasana* was advised.

Shavasana

Rest in *Shavasana* for 45 minutes to one hour after completing the procedure, with body covered with a blanket to maintain the body temperature. During this time, the whole digestive system is given a chance to revitalize itself. Passing urine at this time is perfectly normal.

Special Meal

After *Shavasana* specially prepared food, *Khichari* (rice and Moong lentils with, no or a pinch of salt) with Ghee, was given. Eating this meal at the correct time is essential. Within one hour after the practice proper amount of *Khichari* was given. Sleep should be avoided.

After the procedure, complete rest is essential for the whole day. But not to sleep till the first meal is taken.

Second Meal- Study subjects were advised to prepare *Khichari* for the late afternoon meal,

Then participants were advised with on *Pathya* and *Apathya*.

Results

Table 2 shows the Vitals of the volunteers before and after the *Shankaprakshalana* practice.

Vitals of the participants	Case 1		Case 2		Case 3		Case 4		Case 5		Case 6	
	BT	AT										
BP	120/80mm hg	110/70mm hg	110/70mm hg	100/60mm hg	110/70mm hg	100/60mm hg	100/80mm hg	90/60mm hg	100/70mm hg	100/60mm hg	110/80mm hg	100/70mm hg
Pulse	92mi n ⁻¹	85mi n ⁻¹	90mi n ⁻¹	85mi n ⁻¹	90mi n ⁻¹	83mi n ⁻¹	97mi n ⁻¹	89mi n ⁻¹	92mi n ⁻¹	80mi n ⁻¹	92mi n ⁻¹	92mi n ⁻¹
Weight	56kg	No change	41Kg	No change	47kg	No change	63kg	No change	65kg	No change	62kg	No change
Height	155cm		163cm	-	162cm	-	153cm	-	151cm	-	149cm	-

It has shown that Blood pressure and pulse rate were reduced significantly after practicing the procedure of *Shankaprasshalana*.

Table 3 shows the *Prakriti* types of the volunteers.

<i>Prakriti type</i>	<i>Kapha Pitta</i>	<i>Pitta Kapha</i>	<i>Pitta Vata</i>
No of Participant	3	2	1

Figure 1 shows the distribution of the *Prakriti* types

Table 4 shows the pattern of practicing *Yoga* and onset of *Mala Mutra* and *Vega* in individual participants with the drinking of water

Vega	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6
Drinking water -1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Asana practice	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mala vega	-	-	-	-	-	-
Vamana vega	-	-	-	-	-	-
Drinking water-2	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Asana practice	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mala vega	-	-	-	-	-	-
Vamana vega	-	-	-	-	-	-
Drinking water-3	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Asana practice	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mala vega	-	-	-	✓	✓	-
Vamana vega	-	✓ 2 times	-	-	-	-
Drinking water -4	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Asana practice	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mala vega	✓	-	✓ 3 times	✓	✓	✓
Vamana vega	-	-	-	-	-	-
Drinking water -5	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Asana practice	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mala vega	-	-	-	✓ 3 times	✓	-
Vamana vega	-	-	-	-	-	-
Drinking water -6	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Asana practice	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mala vega	-	✓ 2 times	-	✓	✓	✓ 2 times
Vamana vega	-	-	-	-	-	-
Drinking water -7	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓
Asana practice	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓
Mala vega	-	-	-	-	✓	-
Vamana vega	-	-	-	-	-	-
Drinking water -8	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	-
Asana practice	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	-
Mala vega	-	✓	✓ 2 times	-	✓	-
Vamana vega	-	-	-	-	-	-
Drinking water -9	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-
Asana practice	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-
Mala vega	-	-	✓	-	-	-
Vamana vega	-	-	-	-	-	-

Drinking water - 10	✓	-	✓	-	-	-
Asana practice	✓	-	✓	-	-	-
Mala vega	✓	-	✓	-	-	-
Vamana vega	-	-	-	-	-	-

Mala Vega of 80% of them started after drinking the 6th and 8th glasses of water and all the participants ended up the *Mala Vega* with pale color watery without particles.

Table 5 shows the amount of water intake and onset of Vega

<i>Vega</i>	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6
Drinking water number of the glasses	20	18	20	12	16	14
Times of Asana practice	10	09	10	06	08	07
<i>Mala Vega</i>	02	03	07	06	06	03
<i>Vamana Vega</i>	-	02	-	-	-	01

Figure 2 shows the results of the *Shankprakashana*

According to the figure 1, it has shown that the majority of them were having water intake capacity is more than 12 glasses of water. Half of the participants were had 6 times of onset of *Mala Vega*. Only two participants were had onset of *Vamana Vega*.

Table 6 shows the Relationship between *Prakriti* and *Mala Vega*

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6
<i>Prakriti type</i>	<i>Pitta Vata</i>	<i>Pitta Kapha</i>	<i>Kapha Piita</i>	<i>Kapha Pitta</i>	<i>Kapha Pitta</i>	<i>Pitta Kapaha</i>
<i>Mala Vega</i>	02	03	07	06	06	03

Considering the *Prakriti* types of the research participants' majority of them were *Kapha Pitta*. It was 50% of the sample

Figure 2 shows the relationship between *Prakriti* type and frequency of *Mala Vega* onset

This shows that the frequency of *Mala Vega* onset is high among the *Kapha Pitta prakriti* type and also it has observed that earliest onset of *Mala Vega* seen among the *Kapha Pitta Prakriti* type.

Discussion

Shankhaprakshalana is a *Yogic* intestinal cleansing technique that has been shown to support both disease prevention and the management of certain health conditions. The findings of this study indicate that a single session of *Shankhaprakshalana*, involving the intake of saline water combined with the practice of five specific *Yoga Asanas*, resulted in a significant reduction in blood pressure and effective bowel evacuation.

The physiological mechanism underlying this practice suggests that *Tadasana* facilitates the opening of the pyloric valve, allowing saline water to pass into the small intestine. *Tiryaka Tadasana* further aids in the movement of water through the intestines. *Chakrasana* contributes by promoting the downward movement of stool through peristaltic action. Additionally, *Tiryaka Bhujangasana* supports the opening of the ileocecal valve, facilitating the entry of water into the large intestine. Finally, *Udarakarshanasana* activates the recto-anal inhibitory reflex, promoting defecation. The combined effect of these *Asanas* enhances intestinal cleansing and assists in the elimination of metabolic waste and toxins from the gastrointestinal tract and bloodstream, thereby potentially reducing the risk of metabolic disorders⁽¹²⁾. Further research indicates that regular practice of these *Asanas*, in the absence of a regulated diet, can improve glycemic control and lipid profiles, although it may not lead to significant reductions in body weight¹³.

This study has proved that there is a relationship between frequency of *Mala Vega* onset and the *Prakriti* type of the research participants which is the frequency of *Mala Vega* onset among *Kapha Pitta Prakriti* type is high and also earliest onset seen among them. Relevant to the study done by Divyashree at el, 2020 and Rogad S at el, 2019^{14,15} have found that the *Kapha Pitta Dosha Prakriti* are having *Madhya Koshta* which have softness and solidity, medium quantity of stool an feeling of satisfaction after bowel clearance with moderate urgency. However, when combined with dietary regulation, these practices have been associated with favorable changes in anthropometric measurements, contributing to overall health maintenance and metabolic balance¹⁶.

Conclusion

The results clearly indicate that *Varisara Dhauti* also known as *Shankhprakashalana*, is effective in cleansing the digestive tract and inducing a state of physical and mental relaxation. Once it is practiced, it reduces the vital measurements as pulse and blood pressure of the research participants and also proved that the onset of *Mala Vega* and the frequency is earlier onset and moderate high frequency respectively presented among the participants with *Kapha Pitta* dominant. This practice only increases the mobility of aliment tract. This *yogic* detoxification technique has demonstrated benefits in preventing various digestive disorders and promoting overall health. Furthermore, emerging research suggests that practicing *Shankhprakashalana* at least once a month is safe and beneficial to contribute to significant improvements in quality of life by enhancing digestive efficiency, reducing toxin accumulation, and supporting metabolic health.

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